

CITRATE COMPLEXES OF LEAD. PART II

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The insoluble lead citrate compound, formed by the neutralisation of a citric acid solution containing lead nitrate, is a dibasic acid. The compound is formed by the action of one of the carboxyl groups and the hydroxyl group of the citric acid, and either a five- or a six-membered ring is formed. This insoluble compound dissolves when the p_H is increased due to the formation of another complex (II) in which three co-ordination positions are occupied by a citrate ligand and, most probably, the fourth position by a molecule of water. This contains a free carboxyl group which ionises, followed by the ionisation of the water molecule, affording complex (III) and complex (IV) respectively. The latter ionisation takes place beyond p_H 9. The formation constants of the complexes (II) and (III) and dissociation constants of complex (II) to (III) and complex (III) to (IV) have been determined.

When a solution of citric acid is mixed with lead nitrate, no precipitate is obtained, and pure lead nitrate can be crystallised from such a mixture by slow evaporation if the solution is concentrated with respect to lead nitrate. When a mixture of citric acid and lead nitrate is treated with sodium hydroxide, a curdy white precipitate is obtained which dissolves on stirring. When further alkali is added, a permanent precipitate is obtained. The amount of the precipitate increases at first with increasing amount of alkali and then decreases and ultimately a clear solution is obtained. If the curdy white precipitate is allowed to stand, it becomes crystalline. These observations appeared interesting and it was thought worthwhile to investigate the system thoroughly.

Kety (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1942, 142, 181) has determined the stability constant of lead citrate complex $[PbCit]^-$ by the determination of lead electrode potential. The value of the constant is appreciably variable and has been accounted for as due to the variation of ionic strength. The variation is of the type reported in citrate and gluconate complexes of antimony (Das and Pani, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 527; Patra and Pani, *ibid.*, 1955, 32, 572). The variation in the value of the stability constant might be due to the existence of more than one complexes in the solution. Recently, the equilibrium constant of the reaction of lead ion with citric acid has been determined (*J. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1952, 73, 92). The reaction is represented by

The ligand is divalent and the compound is an acid citrate. Nothing has been reported regarding the structure.

From the investigation of the complexes of trivalent antimony with α -hydroxy-acid, it has become clear that the alcoholic group in the α -hydroxy-acid can be induced to react with the cation, if the oxygen-cation bonds have sufficient covalent character. When the cation is attached to one of the oxygen atoms of the carboxyl group by covalent bond, the hydroxyl group in α -position comes sufficiently near the cation, and a covalent bond is formed, if free, and stable orbitals are available in the cation.

It is expected that α -hydroxy group of hydroxy-acids would react with divalent lead not only due to similar electronic configuration of divalent lead and trivalent anti-

mony, but there is sufficient evidence to establish that lead-oxygen bonds have appreciable covalent character. Lead ion with three vacant p orbitals and a pair of s electrons in the outermost quantum level is not expected to behave as divalent barium or strontium ions (divalent lead has ionic radius intermediate between barium and strontium). Though there is some similarity between the properties of divalent lead and barium, the differences are also appreciable. The structure of lead oxide (Moore Jr. and Pauling, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 1392), oxalato-lead complex and acetylacetonate complex of lead indicate directional nature of lead-oxygen bonds, which is an indication of covalent bond. Four orbitals, three p and probably one d of the same principal quantum level, are used in these compounds. The citrate complexes of divalent lead might be similar to citrate complex of trivalent antimony. Since in the latter, in four co-ordination complexes three p and one d orbital of the same principal quantum number are most probably utilised. It is therefore worthwhile to investigate the citrate complexes of lead more thoroughly.

EXPERIMENTAL

Insoluble Lead Citrate Compound.—An M -citric acid solution (~ 100 c.c.) was mixed with nearly 100 c.c. of $M/4$ lead nitrate solution, and the acid was partially neutralised by adding known amounts of ammonium hydroxide. Three different samples were prepared by adding 25, 50 and 75 c.c. of $2N$ ammonia respectively. The curdy white precipitate obtained was allowed to stand for one day. The crystalline substance obtained was filtered, washed with water, dried at 105° to 110° and analysed for lead content.

The three samples were found to be free of ammonia or ammonium salts, and nitrate. It was therefore assumed that the substance contained lead and citrate. A known amount of the substance (0.2 to 0.3 g.) was dissolved in dilute nitric acid and an excess of potassium chromate was added, followed by a large excess of ammonium acetate solution. The lead chromate was filtered off and chromate content was estimated iodimetrically. The amount of lead was calculated from the amount of chromate. The results are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Samples.	% Pb found.	% Pb calc. for $PbH_6C_6O_7$.
I	{ 51.71 52.07	
II	{ 51.80 51.98	52.16
III	{ 51.66 51.33	

The results indicate the formulae to be $PbH_6C_6O_7$. Citric acid being tribasic and lead being divalent, at least one of the carboxyl groups of citric acid has not been neutralised in the compound. The compound is expected to behave as an acid.

Basicity of the Insoluble Lead Citrate Compound.—It has been mentioned earlier that the compound dissolves when the p_H is increased by adding alkali. A known amount (0.5 g.) of the substance was suspended in water. A small amount of sodium citrate was added and the mixture was titrated against standard alkali using thymolphthalein as an indicator. Sodium citrate was added to prevent hydrolysis. The results are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Samples	...	...	1	2	3
Wt. of the substance (in g.)	...	...	0.4872	0.5064	0.5020
0.1562 N NaOH required (in c.c.)	...	...	15.65	16.20	16.15
Wt. of substance requiring 2 litres of N-NaOH (in g.)	...	...	395.9	397.3	395.1

The formula weight of the substance being 397.32, the above results indicate the substance to be a dibasic acid. Two hydrogen ions of citric acid have been replaced due to the formation of the insoluble compound; two more hydrogen ions cannot be liberated unless the hydroxyl group takes part in the reaction with the liberation of a hydrogen ion. The above observation is further supported by the experiment described below.

A known amount of citric acid was taken and titrated against standard caustic soda using thymolphthalein as an indicator. In another experiment, to the same amount of acid a known amount of a standard lead nitrate solution was added and titrated against the standard NaOH solution. The results are reported in Table III.

TABLE III

Conc. $Pb(NO_3)_2 = 0.104 M$. Conc. NaOH = 0.123 M. Citric acid taken = 20 c.c.

No.	1	2	3	4
$Pb(NO_3)_2$ added (c.c.)	0.0	0.0	10.0	10.0
NaOH reqd. (c.c.)	60.1	60.1	68.3	68.3

The above results indicate that one equivalent of acid per atom of lead is liberated due to the presence of lead nitrate. For further confirmation of the results, the above experiment was repeated in presence of barium nitrate. But no acid was found to be liberated.

The liberation of hydrogen ion from the hydroxyl group of citrate ligand due to the formation of complex with lead most probably takes place. The above experiments, however, do not establish whether the hydroxyl group reacts when the insoluble compound is formed, or at the time of the soluble complex. Further investigation was carried on as described below.

p_H Titration.—Neutralised 0.2M citric acid solution (30% ; 125 c.c.) was mixed with 10 c.c. of 0.04836 M lead nitrate solution. A precipitate was obtained. The p_H of the solution was measured after the addition of increasing amounts of N-NaOH. The results are shown in curve (A) of Fig. 1. In another experiment, the same conditions were maintained except that 10 c.c. of water was added instead of 10 c.c. of lead nitrate. The results are represented by curve (B) of Fig. 1. The horizontal distance between the two curves indicates the amount of acid liberated due to the reaction of lead with citrate. A large amount of citric acid, compared to the amount of lead nitrate, was taken

so that the neutralisation curve of the citric acid would not be affected to any appreciable extent due to the formation of the insoluble compound. The horizontal distance is almost constant throughout and is very nearly equal to one equivalent of acid per atom of lead. It is therefore probable that hydroxyl group reacts at the beginning when the insoluble compound is formed.

FIG 1.

Solubility of the Compound in Partially Neutralised Citric Acid Solution.—The solubility of the compound was determined in partially neutralised citric acid solutions at 35°. In each solvent the concentration of the total citrate was kept constant. The lead contents were determined by precipitating as lead chromate and estimating the chromate iodimetrically. The results are shown in Table IV. It is interesting to note that the solubility of the compound first decreases and then increases with increasing neutralisation of citric acid. The minimum solubility is at about 23 to 24% neutralised solution.

TABLE IV

Conc. of total citrate = 0.5 M.

% Neutralisation	0.0	10.0	20.0	30.0	60.0
G. moles of $Pb(C_6H_5O_7)$ per litre	0.00393	0.001368	0.0006102	0.001069	0.00362

The higher solubility in pure citric acid is evident from the observation that the insoluble compound is not formed when lead nitrate and citric acid are mixed. The addition of sodium hydroxide to the mixture is tolerated to a certain extent till a permanent precipitate appears. It is therefore expected that the compound would dissolve

to certain extent in citric acid and the solubility would decrease with increasing neutralisation of the acid. The increase in the solubility after the minima is due to the formation of a soluble complex at a higher p_{H^+} . If the compound is formed by the action of mono-hydrogen citrate ion (HCit^{2-}) and lead ion, the solubility of the compound would be minimum in 66.6% neutralised solution in which the concentration of HCit^{2-} is maximum. This is, however, not observed. The minimum solubility is observed in solution in which the concentration of dihydrogen citrate ion (H_2Cit^-) is very high. It is therefore reasonable to assume that the H_2Cit^- ion reacts. The reaction can be represented by equation (1) or (2), depending on whether five- or six-membered ring is formed. It is, however, difficult to say which of the two compounds is actually formed. This compound would be expressed as complex (I) or C.

The Soluble Lead Citrate Complex.—Complex (1) dissolves when the p_{H^+} is increased. The reaction may be represented by equation (3). The co-ordination number of lead in the soluble complex is 4. The three co-ordination positions are occupied by the citrate ligand and the fourth by a molecule of water as in the case of citrate complex of antimony (Das and Pani, *loc.cit.*). (The possibility of four co-ordination complex of lead has been discussed earlier).

The free carboxyl group present in the above complex (II) is first neutralised by a hydroxyl ion and complex (III) is formed. The aquo-complex (III) then dissociates into hydroxo-complex (IV) and hydrogen ion still at a higher p_{H^+} . The reactions being

Conductometric Titration.—The conductometric titration of a mixture of citric acid and lead nitrate with alkali qualitatively indicates the reactions (1), (2), (3) and (4). 0.1184 M-citric acid (15 c.c.) was mixed with 0.09596 M lead nitrate solution (10 c.c.). The mixture was diluted with 300 c.c. of conductivity water. The conductance was measured with a dip type electrode after adding increasing amounts of 1.073 N-NaOH solution. The results are graphically shown in Fig. 2.

FIG. 2

The conductance as usual decreases at the beginning due to the neutralisation of fast moving hydrogen ions. When the precipitate is formed, the conductance is very nearly constant (the decrease in conductance is small). Since the amount of hydrogen ion removed by alkali is produced due to the formation of complex (I), the net result of addition of alkali is that, one lead ion and one H_2Cit^- ion are removed and one sodium ion is introduced into the solution. At (B) the reaction (3) commences. For each hydroxyl ion added (the hydroxyl ion is neutralised) a complex (II) is brought and a sodium ion is added to the solution. The conductivity therefore rises. At (C) the whole of the complex (I) is dissolved and the neutralisation of the free carboxyl group of the complex (II) takes place. The p_x rapidly rises and the reaction is complete at (D).

The breaks at (A), (B) and (C) correspond to the beginning of the formation of complex (I), complex (II) and complex (III) respectively. At (D) the formation of the

complex (III) from complex (II) is complete. The formation of complex (IV) is not indicated, since the conductivity of the solution is very high. The formation of the complex (IV) is, however, inferred from the following observations. If sulphuric acid is added to a solution where the condition for the complete formation of the complex (III) is maintained, a white precipitate is immediately obtained. No precipitate is obtained if ammonium sulphate is added. If excess of sodium hydroxide is added, the addition of sulphuric acid does not result in precipitation so long as the excess of sodium hydroxide is not neutralised. The precipitation of lead chromate is also suppressed to a certain extent. The excess of alkali requires neutralisation before any precipitate can be obtained. The added alkali does not appear to be free. Reaction (5) most probable takes place.

Determination of Equilibrium Constant

p_H Titration Method.—A solution (75 c.c.) containing 0.004992 g. moles of sodium citrate and 0.025 g. of potassium nitrate was taken and increasing amounts of 0.05M lead nitrate solution were added and the *p_H* of the resulting solution were measured. The results are graphically shown in Fig. 3. Potassium nitrate was added to the system to keep the ionic strength very nearly constant. The curve indicates that acid is liberated due to the reaction, and thus, the *p_H* of the system is lowered with the increasing amounts of lead nitrate added.

The amount of lead nitrate added being less than the amount of sodium citrate, from the results discussed before it can be assumed that the formation of lead citrate complex is almost complete and the concentration of free lead ion is very small and can be neglected, compared to the concentration of the complex. The complex being a soluble one is assumed to be C^- .

The formation of C^- is complete. Since the *p_H* of the system is maintained above 7, a portion of the complex dissociates into C_1^{2-} and H^+ , and thus, lowers the *p_H* of the system. The reaction is represented by equation (4) and the equilibrium constant by equation (4-1), where $[C^-]$, $[C_1^{2-}]$ and $[H^+]$ represent the molar concentration of complex C^- complex, C_1^{2-} and H^+ ion respectively.

$$\frac{[C_1^{2-}] \times [H^+]}{[C^-]} = K_1 \quad \dots \quad (4-1)$$

The citrate ions (Cit^{3-}) being strongly basic remove the liberated protons with the formation of monohydrogen citrate ion, dihydrogen citrate ion and citric acid. The molar concentration of different ions are represented by square brackets.

$$\text{Total acid liberated} = [\text{C}_1^{2-}] = [\text{H}^+] + [\text{HCit}^{2-}] + 2[\text{H}_2\text{Cit}^-] + 3[\text{H}_3\text{Cit}]$$

$$\text{or } [\text{C}_1^{2-}] - [\text{H}^+] = [\text{HCit}^{2-}] \times \left(1 + 2 \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_2} + 3 \frac{[\text{H}^+]^2}{k_1 \times k_2} \right)$$

$$\text{or} \quad [\text{C}_1^{2-}] - [\text{H}^+] = a \times [\text{HCit}^{2-}] \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

where k_1 and k_2 are respectively the first and second dissociation constants of citric acid.

$[\text{Ct}] = \text{total citrate} = \text{free citrate} + \text{citrate in complex.}$

Free citrate = $[\text{Cit}^{3-}] + [\text{HCit}^{2-}] + [\text{H}_2\text{Cit}^-] + [\text{H}_3\text{Cit}]$

$$= [\text{HCit}^{2-}] \times \left(\frac{k_3}{[\text{H}^+]} + 1 + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_2} + \frac{[\text{H}^+]^2}{k_1 \times k_2} \right)$$

or Free citrate = $b \times [\text{HCit}^{2-}]$.

k_3 is the third dissociation constant of citric acid.

Citrate in the complex = total lead nitrate = $[\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2]$.

$$\text{Hence, } [\text{Ct}] - [\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2] = b \times [\text{HCit}^{2-}] \quad \dots \quad (8)$$

$[\text{Ct}]$ is calculated from the g. moles of sodium citrate added and the total volume. $[\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ is also similarly calculated. The total volume and $[\text{H}^+]$ are obtained from graph; "a" and "b" are calculated taking $k_3 = 3.24 \times 10^{-6}$, $k_2 = 4.07 \times 10^{-5}$ and $k_1 = 8.32 \times 10^{-4}$ (Schwarzenbac and Ackermann, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1949, **32**, 1682). Substituting the values of $[\text{Ct}]$, $[\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ and b in equation (8), $[\text{HCit}^{2-}]$ is obtained. Substituting the values of $[\text{HCit}^{2-}]$ in equation (7), $[\text{C}_1^{2-}]$ is obtained. $[\text{C}^-]$ is obtained by subtracting $[\text{C}_1^{2-}]$ from $[\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2]$. The value of K_1 is calculated by equation (4-1). The values are shown in Table V. The values are fairly constant except the last one, and the average value is 8.08×10^{-8} . Since it is not possible to ascertain the concentration of lead ion, the formation constant of complex (II) or (III) from lead ion and citrate ion cannot be calculated. It was therefore decided to adopt the solubility method.

TABLE V

p^{H} .	$[\text{Ct}] \times 10^3$.	$[\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2] \times 10^3$.	$[\text{C}_1^{2-}] \times 10^3$.	$\text{C}^- \times 10^3$.	$K_1 \times 10^8$.
7.54	6.569	0.846	0.5728	0.2732	6.04
7.38	6.483	1.362	0.8079	0.5541	6.08
7.28	6.400	1.923	0.9922	0.9308	5.60
7.19	6.320	2.543	1.189	1.345	5.71
7.13	6.240	3.125	1.330	1.795	5.50
7.06	6.163	3.777	1.522	2.255	5.87
6.96	5.873	5.886	1.739	3.848	4.96
6.82	5.672	7.386	2.216	5.170	6.49
6.78	5.557	8.333	2.318	6.015	6.39
6.74	5.487	8.792	2.474	6.254	7.20
6.72	5.426	9.239	2.528	6.711	7.18
6.61	5.146	11.340	2.861	8.479	8.26
6.47	4.754	14.290	3.199	11.090	9.78
6.30	4.341	17.400	3.561	13.840	12.90

Solubility Method.—Lead chromate was prepared from G. R. quality lead nitrate and potassium chromate. It was washed, dried at 105° and analysed for chromate content iodimetrically and found 99.9% pure. The solubility of this sample was studied in sodium citrate and in equimolecular mixture of sodium citrate and sodium hydroxide of various concentrations at 35°. The solubility was obtained by estimating the chromate contents of solutions. The p_H was also measured. The results are recorded in Tables VI and VII respectively for sodium citrate and the mixture of sodium citrate and sodium hydroxide systems.

TABLE VI

$[\text{CrO}_4^{2-}] \times 10^4$	p_H	[Ct].	$[\text{Pb}^{2+}] \times 10^{11}$	$[\text{Cit}^{3-}]$	$K_3 \times 10^3$
2.611	8.44	0.25	3.444	0.2497	11.04
2.374	8.48	0.23	3.787	0.2298	9.04
2.232	8.59	0.21	4.029	0.2098	6.79
2.136	8.62	0.20	4.210	0.1998	6.09
1.807	8.64	0.15	4.937	0.1498	5.56
1.519	8.61	0.10	5.917	0.9985	6.32

TABLE VII

$[\text{CrO}_4^{2-}] \times 10^4$	p_H	[Ct].	$[\text{Cit}^{3-}]$	$[\text{Pb}^{2+}] \times 10^{12}$	K_3	$[\text{C}_1^{2-}] \times 10^4$	$[\text{C}_2^{3-}] \times 10^3$	$K_3 \times 10^{10}$
1.229	10.59	0.25	0.2377	0.7821	1.780	5.403	1.1750	5.69
1.120	10.62	0.23	0.2188	0.8035	1.660	5.475	1.0650	4.67
0.8879	10.64	0.21	0.2011	1.014	0.996	6.648	0.8212	2.90
0.8464	10.67	0.20	0.1915	1.063	0.889	7.044	0.7760	2.36
0.8704	10.76	0.15	0.1413	1.034	1.040	6.279	0.8076	2.24
0.6554	10.84	0.10	0.09344	1.373	0.739	6.685	0.5886	1.29

From the p_H titration it is seen that major portion of the complex is in the form of C_1^{2-} at p_H 7.54. The p_H of the solutions of lead chromate in sodium citrate lies between 8.44 and 8.64 and that in equimolecular mixture of sodium citrate and sodium hydroxide between 10.54 and 10.84. It is assumed that in these solutions the concentrations of C^- are very small, and hence, neglected. The solubility of lead chromate being very small, the whole of the lead in the solution is assumed to be present as complex and equal to the concentration of the chromate ion. The concentration of lead ion is obtained by dividing the solubility product of lead chromate (the solubility product at 35° was determined and found to be 1.8×10^{-14}) by the concentration of chromate ion. The concentration of citrate ion was obtained by subtracting the concentration of the complex from total citrate originally taken. The reaction may be represented by

The equilibrium constant is given by

$$\frac{[C_1^{2-}] \times [H^+]}{[Pb^{2+}] \times [Cit^{3-}]} = K_2 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (9-1)$$

The equilibrium constants calculated by equation (9-1) are shown in Tables VI and VII; the values of K_2 are very nearly constant in each series but vary from one series to the other by a factor of 10. The high value of K_2 in higher p_H series is probably due to the dissociation of the water molecule in the complex C_1^{2-} as assumed in the reaction (5). The equilibrium constant K_3 of the reaction is represented by

$$\frac{[C_2^{3-}] \times [H^+]}{[C_1^{2-}]} = K_3 \quad \dots \quad (5-1)$$

Taking K_2 to be 7.47×10^{-2} (the average value in sodium citrate system; Table VI) the values of C_1^{2-} are calculated for the higher p_H series (Table VII); C_2^{3-} is obtained by subtracting $[C_1^{2-}]$ from the total lead. The values, thus calculated, together with K_3 are shown in Table VII, in the last three columns. The average value of K_3 is 3.17×10^{-10} . The equilibrium K of the reaction

can be obtained by dividing K_2 by K_1 (obtained by the p_H titration method). Thus the value of K is 9.3×10^6 .

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